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LEUKOPLAKIA OF THE ORAL MUCOSA: DIAGNOSTICS - THERAPY – PROGNOSIS

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ABSTRACT

In the general structure of providing medical care to patients in dental medical organizations, leukoplakia occurs in the age group of patients from 30 to 70 years, predominantly in men (4.3% compared with 1.9% in women). 100% of cases of patients with leukoplakia of the mouth account for 5.6% of precancerous conditions and 4.87% of cases early cancer. These are patients with verrucous and erosive-ulcerative form of leukoplakia, in whom the state of precancer can transform into invasive squamous cell carcinoma. Incipient or advanced carcinoma oral mucosa due to increased keratinization can mimic leukoplakia. Therefore, any case leukoplakia that is not clearly defined and is not unambiguously benign requires histological and other studies in order to diagnose a precancerous condition or cancer in time.

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OG'IZ BO'SHLIG'I SHILLIQ QAVATINING LEYKOPLAKIYASI: DIAGNOSTIKA - TERAPIYA – PROGNOZ

ANNOTATSIYA

Stomatologik tibbiy tashkilotlarda bemorlarga tibbiy yordam ko'rsatishning umumiy tuzilmasida, leykoplakiya 30 dan 70 yoshgacha bo'lgan bemorlarning yosh guruhida, asosan erkaklarda uchraydi (4,3% ga nisbatan 1,9% ga nisbatan ayollar). Og'iz bo'shlig'i leykoplakiyasi bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 100% holatlari prekanser holatlarning 5,6% va 4,87% holatlarni tashkil qiladi erta saraton. Bular leykoplakiyaning verrukoz va eroziv-yarali shakli bo'lgan bemorlardir, ularda prekanser holati mavjud. Invaziv skuamoz hujayrali karsinomaga aylanishi mumkin. Boshlang'ich yoki rivojlangan karsinom keratinizatsiya kuchayganligi sababli og'iz shilliq qavati leykoplakiyaga taqlid qilishi mumkin. Shuning uchun, har qanday holatda aniq belgilanmagan va bir ma'noda yaxshi bo'lmagan leykoplakiya talab qiladi prekanser yoki saraton kasalligini vaqtida tashxislash uchun gistologik va boshqa tadqiqotlar.

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ЛЕЙКОПЛАКИЯ СЛИЗИСТОЙ РТА: ДИАГНОСТИКА - ТЕРАПИЯ – ПРОГНОЗ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В общей структуре оказания медицинской помощи больным в стоматологических медицинских организациях лейкоплакия встречается в возрастной группе пациентов от 30 до 70 лет, преимущественно у мужчин (4,3% по сравнению с 1,9% у женщин). На 100% случаев обращающихся с лейкоплакией рта приходится 5,6% предраковых состояний и 4,87% случаев раннего рака. Это пациенты с веррукозной и эрозивно-язвенной формой лейкоплакии, у которых состояние предрака может трансформироваться в инвазивный плоскоклеточный рак. Начинаясь или прогрессирующая карцинома слизистой оболочки рта из-за усиленного ороговения может имитировать лейкоплакию. Поэтому любой случай лейкоплакии, который не поддается четкому определению и не является однозначно доброкачественным требует гистологического и других исследований, чтобы вовремя диагностировать предраковое состояние или рак.

Leukoplakia is clinical

Term and therefore does not constitute a diagnosis. The WHO defined in 1997 presented leukoplakia as a predominantly white lesion of the oral mucosa that cannot be characterized as any other definable lesion. In the 2005 WHO classification of tumors of the head and neck (Barnes et al 2005), leukoplakia was not redefined, so it can be assumed that the above definition remains unchanged. The leukoplakia is dealt with under the term precancerous lesions. A precancerous lesion is a morphologically altered tissue in which cancer can occur more likely than in correspondingly normal tissue. Leukoplakia occurs in the male population a prevalence of around 4%, and 1% in the female population (Reichart 2000). Oral leukoplakias are most commonly observed in middle-aged and elderly men. Oral leukoplakia can isolated or multiple. are predilection sites in descending frequency the buccal mucosa, the mucosa of the alveolar process, the floor of the mouth, the Tongue (especially the edge of the tongue), the lips and the Palate. Leukoplakia occurs clinically in two macroscopically distinguishable variants: the homogeneous one (Fig. 1) and the inhomogeneous shape. transitions between both variants are observed (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1: Homogeneous leukoplakia of the buccal mucosa on the right retroangular in chronic cigarette smoker. Fig. 2: Transition between a homogeneous and an inhomogeneous, partly verrucous Leukoplakia of the floor of the mouth.

The homogeneous leukoplakia occurs as a homogeneous whitish. Change in the oral mucosa with flat relief in appearance. The surface is smooth or wavy and has a consistent texture. This form of Leukoplakia is mostly asymptomatic. The inhomogeneous leukoplakia is considered a predominantly white or as white and red variation (Erythroleukoplakia, Fig. 3) defined. This can be irregularly flat, nodular or exophytic. This Forms of leukoplakia can slight discomfort such as pain or burning of the oral mucosa. In addition, the proliferative verrucous Leukoplakia (Fig. 4) has been described. It is characterized by extensive and multifocal, initially Homogeneous, later verrucous changes in the oral mucosa. Often there are no known risk factors. In proliferative verrucous leukoplakia It is an aggressive form of oral leukoplakia that transforms into malignant in almost all cases. This development occurs in four stages: Hyperortho - keratosis without epithelial dysplasia,

verrucous hyperplasia, verrucous carcinoma and finally the conventional one Squamous cell carcinoma (Bagan et al. 2010).

Fig.3: Erythroleukoplakia of the edge of the tongue on the right with alternating white and red areas. Fig. 4: Proliferative verrucous leukoplakia of the gingiva of the anterior mandible. Malignant

Transformations had already occurred by this time.

Generally develop from an inhomogeneous Leukoplakia carcinomas more often than from a homo - Genetic leukoplakia. In principle, the oral However, squamous cell carcinoma can develop from any form of leukoplakia. In addition, it should be noted that some of these carcinomas can also develop without recognizable associated leukoplakia. Most oral leukoplakias can resolve if the etiological factors are avoided etiology The main factor in the development of leukoplakia is the Tobacco. The harmful substances such as tar, nicotine and Nitrosamines are in all cigarettes, and cigars pipe tobacco included. Also the so-called smokeless tobacco, which is used in the form of snuff, and the leaves of the betel nut contain carcinogenic substances. It is estimated that smoking increases the risk of developing an oral plaque - epithelial carcinoma increased by a factor of 20. The mechanism of action of carcinogenic substances the cigarette smoke is in an influencing the DNA replication of keratinocyte stem cells of the oral mucosa (Johnson 2001). The risk of malignant transformation of a flat epithelial dysplasia is caused by the combination of Smoking and excessive chronic alcohol consumption increased by a factor of 50. Microorganisms such as human papillomaviruses (D'Souza 2007), herpes simplex viruses and *Candida albicans* appear to be the most malignant to at least influence the transformation. Differential diagnosis of leukoplakia Leukoplakia is a clinical term, so a number of differential diagnoses are required to make the diagnosis is to be considered. The dignity of these diseases is very different and requires not only a trained examiner but also clinical experience. The Differential diagnoses of leukoplakia are summarized in Table 1. The elaboration of a working diagnosis requires First, take the anamnesis. are to be inquired about Underlying diseases such as diabetes mellitus and high blood pressure, smoking status, skin diseases (e.g. Lichen, Fig. 5 and 6), regular medication and, in particular, medication that has been added in the recent past. The patient should be asked how long the lesion has existed, whether it is painful or whether other symptoms are associated with this lesion. On clinical examination are localization of the leukoplakia, its size and the palpatory impression. Is there a homogeneous or an inhomogeneous leukoplakia? They are also important Symmetry of the lesion and the status of the cervical Lymph nodes (Driemel et al. 2008, Kunkel et al. 2010).

Fig. 5: Plaque-like lichen planus on the back of the tongue. –Fig. 6: Typical histological picture of oral lichen planus with parakeratosis, sawtooth-like rete ridges and the subepithelial, ribbon-like lymphocytic infiltrate, x20, HE.

In problematic cases of leukoplakia, refer to the Internet-based help from the DGZMK. Cell/tissue harvesting methods. In homogeneous leukoplakia without suspicion of malignancy can be used as the primary diagnostic method, the Bürsten biopsy are recommended in every dental practice. This Method provides information about a possibly existing inflammation, to microorganisms, especially *Candida*, to keratinization disorders and to the question an epithelial dysplasia. From day-to-day practice, it is important to note that the anatomical localization of the lesion must be communicated to the oral pathologist, since, for example, a parakeratosis in the buccal mucosa justifies a pathological finding, a parakeratosis of the gingiva however, is physiological. To make a meaningful cytological to enable diagnostics, only one Lesion to be examined when multiple lesions are present to use several brushes accordingly. This should be also noted on the receipt. The Application of a brush swab for the entire Oral mucosa is by no means expedient. In the case of inhomogeneous leukoplakia, in the case of leukoplakia in which epithelial dysplasia was found cytologically by means of a brush biopsy, an adequate diagnosis could not be achieved or the genesis of leukoplakia remains unclear even after the cessation of any stimuli (e.g. tobacco, mechanical irritation, medication). surgical biopsy is the gold standard. Depending on the size and accessibility of the leukoplakia an excision or incision biopsy is indicated. In each In the case of the incision, care must be taken to ensure that mucosa that appears macroscopically healthy is also removed at least at one resection edge.

Microscopic diagnostics

Microscopic diagnostics should be performed by pathologists specializing in oral pathology. There is a pathologist who “knows everything and can do everything”. Not anymore in the 21st century (“Pathologists who believe that they never need a second or specialist opinion are dangerous. Increasingly this becomes true in surgical pathology which is ever more subspecialized and in which the days of the true generalists are numbered.” (Fletcher 2007).

Both on the cell material of the brush biopsy and on the surgically obtained biopsy material are in the specialized pathological practice well-founded statements on morphological changes that are clinical impress as leukoplakia, possible. So e.g. B. Cornifications in the form of parakeratoses or hyperorthokeratoses. A statement on the presence of epithelial dysplasia must be required. If this is verifiable the WHO classification, which differentiates between low, moderate and high grade epithelial dysplasia, is recommended for grading the dysplasia on the histological slide preparation. There are also other schemes, such as B. the Ljubljana classification, which, however, have not been internationally accepted. In the histological assessment of dysplasia flow a series of pathological changes occurring in the

cell nuclei are recognizable, and changes in the architecture, which are detectable in the form of disturbances in the epithelial layering. Low-grade epithelial dysplasia is present when the cytological changes in the keratinocytes are limited to the basal third of the squamous epithelium. The intermediate Epithelial dysplasia is diagnosed when cytological and architectural changes up to the middle Thirds of the epithelium extend beyond it spreading changes are called severe epithelial dysplasia. On the cell material Brush biopsy can definitively identify epithelial dysplasia be diagnosed, but not graduated, because due to the cell isolation in this method, the Stratification of the epithelium is absent and hence cannot be assessed. In addition to the conventional stains (Pap, HE, PAS) other methods can also be used the significance and the diagnostic certainty of the samples obtained in the dental practice increase significantly. These include e.g. B. immunocytological Investigations into the detection of extracellular matrix molecules (e.g. laminin-5) in the cell material of the Bürs Ten biopsy (Driemel et al 2007) and the immunohistological detection of chemokine receptors (Meng et al 2010), which may be used as a biomarker in the future Statement on the prognosis of oral squamous cell carcinoma to allow. In addition, for special questions molecular-biological detection and typing by human papillomavirus (HPV). In cases of histologically proven epithelial dysplasia DNA cytometry indicated. If an aneuploid chromosome set is detected in the dysplastic cells, the risk of developing an oral one is lower than in cells with a diploid chromosome set Squamous cell carcinoma significantly increased (personal communication EW Odell, London).

Therapy

Oral pathology must precede therapy. Diagnosis of a brush biopsy or a Incision or excision biopsy of the leukoplakically changed area of the oral mucosa. The therapy directs based on the microscopic diagnosis, taking into account the clinical and anamnestic findings. in the (most common) cases of smoker's keratosis appears in the urgent notice to renounce this habit obvious. Most patients respond positively to the message that the smoker's keratosis, the Provided the oral mucosa is fully able to regenerate, it can regress after quitting smoking. Candidiasis, superinfected by leukoplakia can occur is treated with antifungal medication. In some cases this way transforms an inhomogeneous form into a homogeneous one will. Often in “stubborn” cases there is also.

Change of antifungal medication required.

In special cases, the typing of the *Candida* species can be considered. In practice, a lichenoid reaction is often suspected as the differential diagnosis of leukoplakia. Here is a detailed medical history is required, paying particular attention to medications that only recently been taken by the patient. A change of medication should always be included be discussed with the family doctor. The treatment of epithelial dysplasia depends on the degree of dysplasia. In this way, lesions with low-grade dysplasia can remain under clinical control not exceed six months (van der Waal 2010). For lesions with moderate or high grade dysplasia the timely complete excision taking along marginally healthy epithelium. Also here are subsequent check-ups are essential. In however, in the clinical studies currently available, there is no scientific evidence that surgical excision of oral epithelial dysplasia precludes the development of oral squamous cell carcinoma (Brennan et al. 2007).

Prognosis of dysplasia

The following rule of thumb applies to the prognosis of flat epithelial dysplasia of the oral mucosa: In about 20% of cases develops a squamous cell carcinoma, about 20% of dysplasias go into regression about, in 40% of cases there is no change and in 20% an enlargement of the lesion must be expected. There is a generally increased risk of malignant transformation in the following cases: female patients, long-standing leukoplakia, non- smoker, leukoplakia at the edge of the tongue or floor of the mouth, inhomogeneous leukoplakia, superinfection with *Candida albicans* and high grade epithelial dysplasia (Ebhardt & Reichart 2009). Basically, a large part of the leukoplakia appears avoidable if education about the negative health effects of smoking is further promoted. Even more important for the diagnosis of Leukoplakia is the stimulation of the dental profession for the routine examination of the entire oral mucosa.

Literature

1. Axell T, Pindborg JJ, Smith CJ, van der Waal I: Oral white lesions with special
2. reference to precancerous and tobacco-related lesions: conclusions of an international symposium held in Uppsala, Sweden, May 18–21 1994. International Collaborative Group on Oral White Lesions. *J Oral Pathol Med* 25, 49–54 (1996)
3. Axell T, Holmstrup P, Kramer IR, Pindborg JJ, Shear M: International seminar on oral leukoplakia and associated lesions related to tobacco habits. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol* 12, 145–154 (1984)
4. Carrozzo M: How common is oral lichen planus? *Evid Based Dent* 9, 112–113 (2008)
5. de Waal J, Dreyer WP: Oral medicine case book 4. Oral leukoplakia. *SADJ* 63. 042–043 (2008)
6. Driemel O, Hertel K, Reichert TE, Kosmehl H: Current classification of precursor lesions of oral squamous cell carcinoma principles of the WHO classification 2005. *Mund Kiefer Gesichtschir* 10, 89–93 (2006)
7. El Naggar A, Reichart PA: World Health Organization Classification of Tumors. Lyon: International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) IARC Press, 2005
8. Fedele S: Diagnostic aids in the screening of oral cancer. *Head Neck Oncol* 1, 5 (2009)
9. Franceschi S, Talamini R, Barra S et al.: Smoking and drinking in relation to cancers of the oral cavity, pharynx, larynx, and esophagus in northern Italy. *Cancer Res* 50, 6502–6507 (1990)
10. Gale N, Pilch BZ, Sidransky D et al.: World Health Organization Classification of Tumors. Lyon: International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) IARC Press, 2005

11. Gupta PC, Mehta FS, Daftary DK et al.: Incidence rates of oral cancer and natural history of oral precancerous lesions in a 10-year follow-up study of Indian villagers. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol* 8, 283–333 (1980)
12. Haroske G, Baak JP, Danielsen H et al.: Fourth updated ESACP consensus report on diagnostic DNA image cytometry. *Anal Cell Pathol* 23, 89–95 (2001)
13. Holmstrup P, Vedtofte P, Reibel J, Stoltze K: Oral premalignant lesions: is a biopsy reliable? *J Oral Pathol Med* 36, 262–266 (2007)
14. Lingen MW, Kalmar JR, Karrison T, Speight PM: Critical evaluation of diagnostic aids for the detection of oral cancer. *Oral Oncol* 44, 10–22 (2008)
15. Lodi G, Porter S: Management of potentially malignant disorders: evidence and critique. *J Oral Pathol Med* 37, 63–69 (2008)
16. Lodi G, Scully C, Carrozzo M, Griffiths M, Sugerman PB, Thongprasom K: Current controversies in oral lichen planus: report of an international consensus meeting. Part 2. Clinical management and malignant transformation. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod* 100, 164–178 (2005)
17. Lodi G, Scully C, Carrozzo M, Griffiths M, Sugerman PB, Thongprasom K: Current controversies in oral lichen planus: report of an international consensus meeting. Part 1. Viral infections and etiopathogenesis. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod* 100, 40–51 (2005)
18. Maraki D, Becker J, Böcking A: Cytologic and DNA-cytometric very early diagnosis of oral cancer. *J Oral Pathol Med* 33, 398–404 (2004)

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